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One of the largest wetland restoration projects in Northern Europe, completed in the year 2000, on the Danish river Skjern.

Identifying site-specific opportunities for implementing Nature-Based Solutions and other nutrient mitigation measures in catchments

EU member states are struggling to reach the targets of the EU Water Framework Directive, which demands most surface waters to be in good ecological status by 2027 (EEA 2024). One of the main pressures on European streams, rivers, lakes and coastal waters comes from excess inputs of nutrients (nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P)) from point and diffuse sources. Closing the gap between current nutrient loadings and concentrations in surface waters and the targets set for different water body types is a major challenge. It requires the use of tools for quantifying the contributions from different sources and for identifying suitable sites for implementation of nutrient reduction measures. This policy brief discusses different approaches to placing nutrient reduction measures in catchments.

A large portfolio of Nature-Based Solutions and other mitigation measures (hereafter collectively referred to as nutrient reduction measures) is available to catchment managers and stakeholders to reduce nutrient losses at the source (e.g. field) or intercept nutrients during their mobilization and transport from source areas to surface waters. Landowners are often compensated for implementing such measures.

In most catchments, combinations of different nutrient reduction measures will be necessary to achieve nutrient reduction targets that are estimated based on current nutrient loads and thresholds for good chemical and/or ecological status of streams, lakes, and receiving coastal waters.

Types of nutrient reduction measures.

The NORDBALT-ECOSAFE project aims to foster the implementation of innovative Nature-Based Solutions and mitigation measures in the Nordic-Baltic region of Europe to reduce diffuse nutrient losses from agriculture and forestry under current and future climate conditions. The partners in NORDBALT-ECOSAFE are from Denmark (lead), Norway, Sweden, Finland, Latvia, and Poland.

Placement of nutrient reduction measures in catchments

In many countries, national guidelines for the use and dimensioning of nutrient reduction measures exist but guidance on their placement within a catchment is often lacking and implementation of measures is not planned at relevant spatial scales (e.g. catchment scale).

There are various factors that impact the suitability of locations within a catchment for implementation of a measure and its nutrient reduction efficiency:

- ⇒ Terrain, soil, and land use characteristics: Criteria to identify suitable locations for implementation of a practice can be defined for various measures and spatially processed using Geographic Information Systems (GIS).
- ⇒ Nutrient source areas: The amount of nutrient reduction a measure can potentially achieve depends on its location relative to critical source areas and along nutrient transport pathways. These can be identified using eco-hydrological models like SWAT+.
- ⇒ Local/regional land use planning: Conflicts with other planned land uses can decrease the number and area of potential locations for implementing measures.
- ⇒ Stakeholder preferences: When all potential measures and their potential locations in a catchment are identified, different scenarios can be developed that would achieve the targeted nutrient reduction. Letting stakeholders select their preferred scenario can potentially foster implementation of nutrient reduction measures.

The SWAT+ model

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (Arnold et al. 1998) is a catchment-scale model developed for predicting the impacts of land use and agricultural management practices on variables such as flow, sediment, and nutrients under varying climatic and environmental conditions. SWAT+ is a restructured version of the model with enhanced capabilities to represent hydrological connectivity and small-scale processes within catchments (Bieger et al. 2017).

Odense Fjord Catchment in Denmark

The Odense Fjord Catchment in Denmark is one of six case study areas in NORDBALT-ECOSAFE. It is located on the Island of Funen and has a catchment area of 1050 km². Soil types are dominantly loamy and land use is dominated by arable land (64%), urban areas (12%), and natural land (14%).

Diffuse sources are the dominant nutrient source in the Odense Fjord Catchment, amounting to 86% for total N and 52% for total P. The 3rd River Basin Management Plan by the Danish Ministry of Environment stipulates that N loadings to the Odense estuary should be reduced by 420 tons N or 29% compared to current baseline loadings.

In this policy brief, we present two examples of strategies to identify suitable areas for implementing wetlands as nutrient reduction measures that were applied in the Odense Fjord Catchment.

Wetlands

Wetlands are a common nutrient reduction measure in Denmark and the entire Nordic-Baltic region, especially Surface Constructed Wetlands (SCW) on fields or in streams and restored wetlands in riparian areas. SCWs are used to treat drainage water and/or surface runoff from fields (field SCWs) or streamflow (in-stream SCWs), while restored wetlands remove N and P from all pathways including river water during flood events.

In both types of wetlands, nitrogen and phosphorus are removed and/or retained through various processes (denitrification, sedimentation, adsorption, uptake). Restored wetlands also provide multiple co-benefits, because they function as carbon sinks and biodiversity hotspots, retain water in the landscape, and often benefit local recreation.

Conceptual drawing (Carstensen et al. 2020) and photo of a surface constructed wetland in Fillerup, Denmark.

Example 1: Local involvement in wetland restoration planning

In autumn 2023, NORDBALT-ECOSAFE contributed to the work of “Odense Fjord”, a Coastal Water Board for the Odense Fjord Catchment.

In Denmark, the planning of future land use and reservation of areas (e.g., for urban expansion, drinking water abstraction areas, afforestation, nature conservation) lies within the responsibility of the municipalities. Therefore, representatives of the municipalities were involved in the Coastal Water Board work to actively exclude the potential riparian wetland areas where the municipality has other future plans for use of the areas.

The process involved multiple steps:

1. Delineation of floodplains, which are the most suitable areas of a catchment for restoring wetlands, using the SWAT+ interface.
2. Exclusion of urban areas as they are unsuitable for wetland restoration.
3. Review of map during a Coastal Water Board workshop and exclusion of additional areas that are unsuitable for wetland restoration due to local planning in the seven municipalities (partly) located in the Odense Fjord catchment.
4. Development of an optimistic and a conservative scenario based on workshop outcomes and two maps of already existing wetlands.
5. Implementation and simulation of scenarios in SWAT+.

Lively discussions during the Coastal Water Board meeting on October 9, 2023 in Odense, Denmark.

Floodplains in the Odense Fjord Catchment delineated by the SWAT+ interface and areas within the floodplains identified as suitable for wetland restoration after consideration of urban areas, local land use planning, and existing wetlands.

Scenarios 1 and 2 resulted in an increase in wetland area of 79 and 55 km², respectively. It was also assumed that after restoration, subsurface drains from agricultural areas would discharge into the riparian wetlands instead of Odense River and its tributaries.

The SWAT+ model simulated a reduction in total N loadings to the Odense estuary of 39% for scenario 1 and 26% for scenario 2. For both scenarios, the estimated total N-reduction was highest during the winter and lowest during the summer.

Average monthly reduction in total N loads to Odense Fjord simulated by SWAT+ for the two scenarios.

Example 2: Mapping of suitable sites for surface constructed wetlands

In Denmark, SCW are allowed to be constructed by farmers if they follow the national guidelines. Since 2017, the Agricultural Agency in Denmark has had one or two open calls per year for farmers to apply for full economic support for constructing a SCW. In addition, catchment officers were trained to support farmers in finding suitable sites for SCWs and assist them in the application process.

Also, a national map of suitable, possibly suitable, and unsuitable sites for SCWs on fields was created based on local tile drainage conditions, farmed areas, riparian areas, and nitrate leaching.

The map of SCWs in the River Odense catchment shows that a total of 127 SCWs can potentially be constructed with a reduction in N-loading to the Odense estuary amounting to ca. 4% of baseline loading.

Placement of 127 potential surface constructed wetlands and their drainage areas in the Odense Fjord Catchment (Andersen 2024).

A new River Basin Management Support System

Using the Odense Fjord Catchment in Denmark as an example, we demonstrated how the SWAT+ model can be used in combination with local knowledge to map potential sites for restoring riparian wetlands and estimating the potential reduction in N loads. Also, we presented a map that provides support to farmers for identifying potential locations for the implementation of constructed wetlands. However, a comprehensive tool to guide catchment managers, municipalities, and other stakeholders is not available.

Therefore, NORDBALT-ECOSAFE is developing a new tool for identifying site-specific opportunities for implementation of nutrient reduction measures. Main inputs are geo-spatial data, SWAT+ outputs on nutrient source areas and transport pathways, and potentially information about local land use planning. Using GIS-based analyses of the main inputs, placement opportunities can be identified for different nutrient reduction measures. The resulting maps can be used to estimate the effect of individual measures on nutrient loads using SWAT+ and to develop possible catchment management scenarios with various combinations of measures, which can then also be simulated in SWAT+. Catchment-specific nutrient reduction targets defined by comparing the safe ecological boundaries quantified in NORDBALT-ECOSAFE for different types of water bodies to the baseline nutrient loads simulated by SWAT+ can be used to estimate the performance of the different catchment management scenarios in achieving a sufficient reduction in nutrient loads. Finally, the most effective scenarios can be discussed with stakeholders to identify those that are viable with regard to both their effectiveness and stakeholder preferences.

The system will be tested in the six NORDBALT-ECOSAFE case study areas in Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Latvia, and Poland.

An innovative Swedish approach to placing in-stream surface constructed wetlands

Djordjic et al. (2020) developed a three-step modelling approach for identifying suitable locations for in-stream SCWs in four different size groups (0.1–1.0 ha) and tested it in the Lillån Catchment (192 km²) in Central Sweden. SCWs were placed based on incoming hydraulic and P load. Subsequently, the P retention was modelled for 191 potential wetlands in the catchment. The estimated P retention varied considerably between the SCWs, which suggests a high potential for targeted placement to increase the cost-efficiency of in-stream SCWs.

Flowchart of the NORDBALT-ECOSAFE River Basin Management Support System (under development).

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The NORDBALT-ECOSAFE consortium will develop and demonstrate innovative methods and establish best practices to improve current river basin management and governance by reaching the following major aims: i) setting ecologically safe nutrient boundaries in different types of water bodies; ii) improving monitoring of nutrient concentrations by comparing benefits of novel high-frequency online sensors with traditional monitoring; iii) establishing nutrient loading tipping points for carbon sequestration and emissions in water bodies; iv) establishing a harmonised river basin modelling tool for precise estimation of nutrient sources, pathways and transport; v) demonstrating novel Nature Based Solutions (NBSs) and Mitigation Measures (MMs) for reaching the required nutrient load reductions; and vi) developing advanced solutions supporting regional governance structures to implement the most suitable measures to meet the ecological nutrient boundaries. A conceptual diagramme is showing the links between different parts of the project and a map shows our working platform consisting of six river basins and riverine monitoring points under HELCOM and OSPAR. Learn more under: <https://projects.au.dk/nordbalt-ecosafe>.